

D4.5 BMS Validation

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Executive summary

This report contains the validation of the BMS developed in the framework of project MARBEL during the commissioning phase to ensure proper operation during the testing phase. The scope of the report is limited to the innovation present in the novel system.

Table of contents

Deliverable Information sheet.....	2
Executive summary	2
Table of contents	3
List of figures	4
List of abbreviations	5
Introduction.....	6
1. Battery Management System innovations.....	7
2. Validation of innovations	7
2.1 Wireless communications.....	7
2.2 Cloud connectivity	9
3. CONCLUSIONS	14
4. REFERENCES	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
5. ANNEXES	¡Error! Marcador no definido.

List of figures

Figure 1: Module with cell-attached iSCMs	7
Figure 2: Cell voltages (in mV) transmitted wirelessly (only 3 cells are displayed)	8
Figure 3: Module voltage (in V) transmitted wirelessly (only 1 module is displayed).....	8
Figure 4: Pack average temperature (in °C) computed from cell temperatures, BMS temperature is also displayed	9
Figure 5: MARBEL Battery Pack used during the commissioning phase to validate the BMS innovations	9
Figure 6: MARBEL BMS used during the battery commissioning.....	10
Figure 7: State-of-Charge (SoC in %) computed by the local BMS in MARBEL Battery Pack...	10
Figure 9: Fully assembled MARBEL battery pack after commissioning	13

List of abbreviations

<i>BP</i>	<i>Batteries Packs</i>
<i>iSCM</i>	<i>Integrated Smart Cell Manager</i>
<i>EV</i>	<i>Electric Vehicles</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>BMS</i>	<i>Battery Management System</i>

Introduction

In this report the innovations developed at BMS level in the framework of the MARBEL project are validated. The validation process is executed during the battery commissioning to ensure that the novel functionalities work correctly before shipment to testing facilities. The tests performed at End-of-Line are aimed to verify that the system operates correctly leaving out of the scope to measure the system performance.

1. Battery Management System innovations

In general terms the BMS is device that monitors the battery status and supervise the battery operation. Among other duties the BMS is in charge of providing the data generated within the battery pack, this information can be divided into: a) measured data (typically voltage, current and temperature) and b) computed data (State-of-Charge and State-of-Health).

The BMS also performs other standard actions such as triggering alarms and warnings, balancing charge and setting a communications link with other external devices that require data from the battery to operate correctly.

The BMS developed in MARBEL captures the following main innovations:

- Wireless communications: the data measured from the cells is transmitted to the BMS via RF-based communications link
- Cloud connectivity: the measured data can be transmitted to the cloud where advanced algorithms provide highly accurate SoX estimations
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2. Validation of innovations

After assembly of the battery pack the BMS is commissioned to ensure proper functionality. These tests encompass several steps, here there are highlighted those used to verify that the novel technical developments are performing as expected.

2.1 Wireless communications

The data at cell level is captured by the integrated Smart Cell Manager (iSCM) and transmitted wirelessly to the BMS that collects the data. The iSCM is attached to the cells as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Module with cell-attached iSCMs

In order to validate the correct operation of the wireless system the data from the cells is captured and displayed as in the following figures.

Figure 2: Cell voltages (in mV) transmitted wirelessly (only 3 cells are displayed)

Figure 3: Module voltage (in V) transmitted wirelessly (only 1 module is displayed)

Figure 4: Pack average temperature (in °C) computed from cell temperatures, BMS temperature is also displayed

As can be seen in Figures 2 to 4 the data is transmitted correctly from the cells and the BMS is able to perform calculation with it, verifying that the data is gathered properly without major deviations or transmission errors.

2.2 Cloud connectivity

To test the connectivity of the BMS the battery pack is connected to a gateway that establishes a link between the cloud and the local BMS. The battery pack and BMS used are shown in Figs. 5 and 6.

Figure 5: MARBEL Battery Pack used during the commissioning phase to validate the BMS innovations

Figure 6: MARBEL BMS used during the battery commissioning

The BMS itself can compute the SoC with an ECM algorithm, the resulting data is displayed in Fig. 7

Figure 7: State-of-Charge (SoC in %) computed by the local BMS in MARBEL Battery Pack

With the data transmitted to the cloud advanced AI-based algorithms are used to compute additional battery indicators, the data is displayed using a dashboard designed for that purpose, all details on this feature can be found in D4.1. Additionally, a firmware update can be performed from the cloud to improve or adapt the BMS software in case of need. The following screenshots show the results from cloud connection and data transfer as tested in laboratory.

Figure 7: Gateway retrieves firmware from cloud after BMS request.

Figure 8: BMS's status sent to Gateway is stored into cloud database

Figure 9: Data published in cloud via MQTT Broker (top) and firmware stored into database (bottom)

Figure 10: MQTT broker gateway-cloud interface (left) and gateway hardware under test (right)

Finally, the pack is ready to proceed with the testing phase, the assembly procedure is completed and the battery is prepared for shipment, as shown in the following figure.

Figure 11: Fully assembled MARBEL battery pack after commissioning

3. CONCLUSIONS

The BMS is validated successfully and the innovations introduced are operating correctly yielding a fully functional battery pack ready to undergo the testing phase where the performance of the system will be evaluated.